

HORIZON EUROPE 2023 Single-Stage Cluster 1 Health Calls Evaluation

Topic Specific Briefing for Experts

HORIZON-HLTH-2023-TOOL-05-03: Integrated, multi-scale computational models of patient patho-physiology ('virtual twins') for personalised disease management

12 May 2023

The Evaluation Process

- Individual Evaluation
- Consensus meeting (Fast track)
- Quality-check by EC staff

Todos

- Cross-reading – Evaluators (preparation for the Panel)
- Panel Meeting- the final meeting involving Evaluators & Recorders

Top proposals

The Individual Evaluation Report (IER)

- Excellence →(0-5)
- Impact →(0-5)
- Implementation → (0-5)
- Other
 - Clinical Study, ethics...

The Individual Evaluation Report (IER)

¿Por qué se penaliza?

Excellence

- Scope?
- Beyond the state of the art?
- No quantified information
- Scientific Methodology

Cómo se va a hacer, **clave!**

La mayoría flojean en este apartado.

HORIZON-HLTH-2023-TOOL-05-03:

Integrated, multi-scale computational models of patient pathophysiology ('virtual twins') for personalised disease management

Scope

Develop multi-scale and **multi-organ**, dynamic, interoperable, modular computational models, capable of accurately simulating the individual patient patho-physiology, spanning different anatomical scales

Advance the state of the art in multi-scale modelling by employing diverse modelling methodologies, including but not limited to: mechanistic modelling, artificial intelligence, agent-based, network physiology for modelling the **healthy state, disease onset, progression, treatment and recovery**. **Availability of the necessary diverse data types must be demonstrated.**

Integrate standardized, spatiotemporal multi-scale models as a basis for developing personalised 'virtual twin' models taking account of patient individual characteristics, user needs and requirements.

Validate patient-specific models and **generate evidence** of clinically meaningful, real-world observations for diseases under study. PoC, feasibility studies in user environments and/or real-world settings are to collect evidence of utility vis-à-vis current clinical practice. Dynamic VHT models will need be shown to improve prognosis, diagnosis, treatments, outcomes, incl. co-morbidities and long-term care.

Develop an exploitation strategy and business plan, with regulatory and industrial input for accelerating clinical and/or market uptake.

Excellence

- Others:
 - Robustness of AI algorithms
 - Clinical Study
 - Social Science and Humanities
 - Open Science
 - Gender Issues
 - ...

Impact

- Expected outcomes and wider impacts? → Mirar bien el “call”
- The scale and significance of the proposal → Cuanta gente se beneficia y cuánto
- The potential barriers (to the expected outcomes and impacts)
- The strategy for dissemination and communication and the exploitation plan.

HORIZON-HLTH-2023-TOOL-05-03:

Integrated, multi-scale computational models of patient patho-physiology ('virtual twins') for personalised disease management

- **Expected outcomes**

- Clinicians, other healthcare professionals have access to and/or use validated multi-scale computational models of individual patients, for delivering optimized, cost-effective patient management strategies superior to the current standard of care.
- Healthcare professionals benefit from enhanced knowledge of complex disease aetiology and progression by recourse to validated, multi-scale and multi-organ models.
- **Clinicians and patients benefit from new, improved personalised diagnostics, medicinal products, devices, and therapeutic strategies** tailored to the individual patient patho-physiology.
- Citizens and patients access validated 'virtual twin' models enabling integration of citizen-generated data with medical and other longitudinal health data, and benefit from early disease detection, prediction of disease progression, treatment options, effective disease management.

Quality of Implementation

- Workplan (timeline, balanced, justified, Gant)
- Risks (Identified?, mitigation measures?)
- Consortium composition (clinical-technical, previous experience in EU projects...)

Consensus Meeting

Top proposals

- Cross-reading
- Panel meeting
- Ranking